

EFFECTIVENESS OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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ABSTRACT: Modern information technologies are developed every year. Today they are used in virtually all areas of human life. This work investigates the impact of using information communication technologies in system of higher education on the example of modular object-oriented dynamic learning environment LMS Moodle. The results obtained testify the effectiveness of the use of such technologies, in particular, to increase the level of motivation and activation of informative activity.

KEY-WORDS: learning, information and communication technology, Moodle, learning efficiency.

I. INTRODUCTION

Information technology value increases and becomes more significant from year to year. Today it is difficult to imagine any area of human activity without information and communication technologies (ICT). The term "technology" has come to us from the Greek language, and translated as "science". The modern understanding of the word includes the application of engineering and scientific knowledge to solving specific practical problems [1]. The ICT refers to the processes and methods of interaction with information, which implemented with the use of devices, computers, and telecommunications [2].

Education is no exception. ICT is used to prepare students at all levels: primary, secondary and higher. Computerization of modern society is connected with the reform of the educational activity. ICT is used for data transmission to ensure the interaction between the teacher and student in the modern system of distance and open education. Initiative of broader use of modern technologies includes student, educational institutions and teachers adjusting to their needs. The Ministry of education strongly promotes the development and implementation of information technologies. This contributes the empowerment of schools, and increases access to education for people. The higher education subject to this more than any other sphere. A few years ago, students used newspapers and magazines to find information, but now it is the exception rather than the rule. In this regard and revise the library role is reduced to introducing electronic databases, electronic versions of educational publications, etc.

Now many research works on the effectiveness of the use of information and communication technologies are actively conducted. The academics' and undergraduates' usage of Twitter is also researched [3]. The effects of teaching approaches and strategies on students' learning achievements and interests as well as the use of distinct teaching strategies and approaches for the promotion of teaching effectiveness considered as the research motivation [4]. Some authors have found a negative or statistically insignificant relationship between the number of online leisure hours and academic achievement, which suggests that the potential of Internet to distract exceed its productive potential [5-9]. However, despite some shortcomings, the obvious fact couldn't be denied: modern teacher should professionally use information and communication technologies in the learning process.

II. CLASSIFICATION OF ICT TOOLS

Areas of methodological tools of information and communication technologies are divided as:

1. Educational - report of knowledge, skills or practical learning activities, providing the required level of mastery Of the content

2. Reference and information search – organizing information.
3. Simulators – development of different skills, consolidate or repetition of the lesson.
4. Demonstrative – visualize the studied phenomena, processes, objects for the purpose of study and research.
5. Simulation – represent some aspect of reality, allowing studying its functional and structural characteristics.
6. Modelling – give you a model of the object or phenomenon for the purpose of study and research.
7. Laboratory – allow to conduct experiments on models of existing equipment.
8. Settlement – automate calculations and various routine operations.
9. Training games - designed to create learning situations which activates the learners in the form of game.

III. ELECTRONIC LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

The main means of ICT-technologies for information environment of the education system is a personal computer equipped with necessary software (system and applied nature, as well as tools). The last few years, LMS Moodle (Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment) become widespread. It is a course management system (CMS), also known as a learning management system (LMS) or virtual learning environment (VLE). This free web application, used in 160 countries, provides an opportunity for the teachers to create effective websites for online learning.

In traditional e-learning, teachers design sets of Learning Objects (LOs) and organize their sequencing; the material implementing the LOs could be either built anew or adopted from elsewhere (e.g. from standard-compliant repositories) and reused [10].

The project of the World Technological University, proposed the implementation of online University based on LMS Moodle, providing a full cycle of student learning in a particular occupation, including access to state certification [11].

Learning Management System (LMS) as a pervasive computing can be embedded in classroom pedagogy to support learning inside and outside the classroom. LMS can play a supportive role to teachers and administrators in higher education to facilitate them in their work. This becomes more significant to the teachers and administrators, when the LMS based on the cloud-computing platform [12].

The wide functionality of the system test questions is also worth mentioning [13]. Teachers can use an authoring tool to create large pools of different types of questions, including multiple choice, open answer, generative questions and complex tasks. System can be used for formative and summative assessment and incorporates different learning elements, including scaffolding features, such as hints, feedback, and misconceptions [14].

The convenience of the medium is achieved by a wide range of functional options:

- Placing content which was created in external software products (including files of different formats);
- Creation of materials (the built-in HTML editor);
- Creation materials for control of knowledge and collaboration of students (tests, assignments, seminars, wikis, Forum etc.
- Monitoring of training;
- Communication course (forums, chats, webinars);
- Feedback (surveys, questionnaires).

IV. RESEARCH

In 2015/2016 academic year at the National research Tomsk Polytechnic University, educational process on discipline "Kinetics of nuclear reactors" was realized using a Moodle LMS. The course was divided into 5 modules.

Discipline includes 56 hours with 32 hours for lectures, 16 hours for practice lessons and 8 hours for laboratory works. Consequently, all works were organized through the electronic environment, in varying degrees.

The first section of the e-learning course "Guide to the course, news", contains the functional and regulatory components: the metadata of the course; introduction of course (video); information about discipline; information about the teacher; forum; chat; glossary; working program; examination questions and references to the sources.

Lecture material for each module is placed in the form of presentations, presented in PDF format and files with full theoretical information in HTML format. For increased functionality and interactivity of theoretical material it was placed in HTML.

Individual files contain animated illustrations and hyperlinks for additional information. Almost all graphs and diagrams are presented in GIF format. Placing files in HTML format allowed us to integrate video from YouTube.

In the implementation of laboratory and practical tasks the tool "Task with a response file" was used. It is DYNKO LAB program, which implements the laboratory work and the license to use the necessary electronic keys. Therefore, the laboratory work students perform in the Department, with electronic keys, and the reports are sent to the teacher via Moodle.

V. RESULTS

To assess the effectiveness of the use of information and communication technologies a comparative analysis of two groups of students was conducted. In the control group (n = 42) training on the subject "Kinetics of nuclear reactors" was conducted in traditional learning without use of electronic platform LMS Moodle. In the experimental group (39 persons) the functionality of the ICT was actively used.

Evaluation criteria:

- The level of material possession (possession);
- The extent of the interest to material (interest);
- Formation of positive motivation (motivation);
- Level of cognitive activity (activity);
- The application of acquired knowledge in different learning situations (application).

The results indicate that using ICT in the learning process causes the indicators to be higher (Figure. 1) than during traditional training (Figure. 2). The largest indicators are marked for level of cognitive activity. This is due to increased involvement and autonomy of students in the course.

For the reliability of the results the statistically significant differences between the results of ascertaining and forming experiments using the X² method (1) was calculated. The obtained value of X² is greater than the critical X²_{kr} = 5.99 (at the significance level of 0.05), with the exception of the last criteria (table1). This equation illustrates a statistically significant change in the results of the experiment.

$$X^2 = \sum (f_0 - f_e)^2 / f_e$$

Figure 1. Evaluation criteria for the learning using ICT

Figure 2. Evaluation criteria for traditional teaching

Table 1. Statistically significant differences χ^2

Level	Evaluation criteria Experimental (f_0)/Control (f_c) group				
	Possession	Interest	Motivation	Activity	Application
High	22/14	20/13	21/13	22/14	20/19
Medium	13/20	15/2	15/20	12/20	16/17
Low	4/5	4/4	3/6	5/5	3/3
χ^2	7.221	5.997	7.673	7.771	0.111

The use of information and communication technologies had almost no impact on students with low performance. In our opinion, this is due to the initial low motivation and disinterest in learning in general.

VI. CONCLUSION

The development and implementation of ICT in the educational process solves a number of important and relevant didactic tasks:

1. Individualization of the learning process.
2. Activation of cognitive activity.
3. Increasing access of students to modern scientific data.
4. Increasing of the level of motivation.
5. Reduced training time.
 $\alpha + \beta = \chi$.
6. The extension of the teaching capabilities of the teacher.

Of course, the use of information and communication technologies in the learning process has some drawbacks. In our opinion, the principal ones are reduction of time of direct communication between teacher and student, as well as decrease in the level of practical training on real equipment [15] (in case of laboratory works carried out using computer programs). However, the fact remains: ICT technologies are the future of the education system.

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